

The activity of some Agomirs and Antagomirs as non small lung carcinoma suppressor

La actividad de algunos Agomirs y Antagomirs como supresores de carcinomas de pulmón no pequeño

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Abstract

Background: non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) development, from tumor initiation to progression and metastasis play roles in cell proliferation, apoptosis, angiogenesis, epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition, migration, invasion, and metastatic colonization, as well as immunosuppression.

Objective: To evaluate the agomirs, sense antagomir, and anti-sense sequences of the most effective ncRNA as a therapeutic tools via gene silencing, due to regression of A549 lung epithelial cell line cell line.

Methods: Three non coding RNA molecules were transfected into cell lines, two of them were micro RNAs (microRNA135a and microRNA34a) agomir molecules and one was long non coding RNA (Adenovirus-HOX Antisense Intergenic RNA) sense molecules, in addition to other two molecules of antagomir of same microRNAs and one antisense molecules represented HOTAIR. Cell viability utilizing XTT (2,3-Bis-(2-Methoxy-4-Nitro-5-Sulfophenyl)-2HTetra-zolium-5-Carboxanilide) was detected. Transfection efficiency of ncRNAs was determined by Real Time qPCR,

Results: Cell viability showed significant value with (microRNA135a and microRNA34a, HOTAIR) agomirs and sense molecule and antagomirs and antisense molecule of the same non coding RNA. WI38 cell line viability values were increased with all most agomirs and sense and sense transfection. Cell line images under inverted microscope showed a clear inhibition of cell line proliferation after transfection with antisense and antagomir molecule. Target gene expression in A549 cell line after molecule transfection showed insignificant upregulation of *TGF-β* and *VEGF*, *TNF* and *SMAD* while high up regulating of *TP53*, *CASPASE8* and *IFNG* with antagomirs and antisense molecule.

Conclusion: The therapeutic mir34 index of transfection elevated A549 cell line regression and consider as promising program for lung carcinoma treatment.

Keywords: non-small cell lung carcinoma; non-coding RNA; gene expression, cell viability.

Resumen

Antecedentes: el desarrollo del cáncer de pulmón de células no pequeñas (NSCLC), desde la iniciación del tumor hasta la progresión y la metástasis, juega un papel en la proliferación celular, la apoptosis, la angiogénesis, la transición epitelial a mesenquimatoso, la migración, la invasión y la colonización metastásica, así como la inmunosupresión.

Objetivo: Evaluar las secuencias agomirs, sense antagomir y antisentido del ncRNA más eficaz como herramienta terapéutica a través del silenciamiento génico, debido a la regresión de la línea celular de la línea celular epitelial pulmonar A549.

Métodos: Se transfirieron tres moléculas de ARN no codificante en líneas celulares, dos de ellas eran moléculas agomir de microARN (microRNA135a y microRNA34a) y una era moléculas sentido largas de ARN no codificante (ARN intergénico antisentido de adenovirus-HOX), además de otras dos moléculas de antagomir de los mismos microRNAs y una molécula antisentido representada HOTAIR. Se detectó la viabilidad celular utilizando XTT (2,3-bis-(2-metoxi-4-nitro-5-sulfofenil)-2HTetrazolio-5-carboxanilida). La eficiencia de transfección de los ncRNA se determinó mediante qPCR en tiempo real,

Resultados: La viabilidad celular mostró un valor significativo con (microRNA135a y microRNA34a, HOTAIR) agomirs y molécula sentido y antagomirs y molécula antisentido del mismo ARN no codificante. Los valores de viabilidad de la línea celular WI38 aumentaron con la mayoría de los agomirs y la transfección sentido y sentido. Las imágenes de líneas celulares bajo microscopio invertido mostraron una clara inhibición de la proliferación de líneas celulares después de la transfección con moléculas antisentido y antagomir. La expresión del gen diana en la línea celular A549 después de la transfección de la molécula mostró una regulación al alza insignificante de *TGF-β* y *VEGF*, *TNF* y *SMAD*, mientras que la regulación al alza de *TP53*, *CASPASE8* e *IFNG* con antagomirs y moléculas antisentido.

Conclusión: El índice terapéutico mir34 de transfección elevó la regresión de la línea celular A549 y se considera un programa prometedor para el tratamiento del carcinoma de pulmón.

Palabras clave: carcinoma de pulmón de células no pequeñas; ARN no codificante; expresión génica, viabilidad celular.

Lung cancer was the most common cause of death from cancer with more than 1.38 million deaths worldwide^{1,4,9}. It accounts for the 80% of all lung cancers, and the main types are: adenocarcinoma (32-40%, squamous 25-30%, large cell 8-16%), despite surgical resection and the development of new chemotherapy regimens, many NSCLC patients relapse and become fatal^{2,10,18}. Consequently, treatment for NSCLC is now moving beyond conventional chemotherapy with the advent of molecular-targeted therapies, currently, angiogenesis quantification to assess and predict the efficacy of antiangiogenic drugs is mainly based on the evaluation of micro-vascular density, but this procedure is highly invasive, and its association with the clinical outcome is uncertain in many tumor types, like NSCLC^{3,20,25}.

There are variety assays present for diagnosing cancers, gene silencing by micro (miRNA) has greatly evolved in a very short period of time^{4,22,16}. micro RNA(miRNA) molecules mediate this extremely conserved process of post-transcriptional gene silencing with a length of 21-23 nucleotides^{5,7,9}.

The lncRNAs are composed of more than 200 nucleotides without production of proteins^{6,13,17}. They are irregularly expressed in a variety of cancer cells and play a key role in a number of cancer symptoms^{7,11,9}. In general, lncRNAs alter gene expression at numerous levels, including chromatin modification, transcription and post-transcription^{8,12,15}.

In Iraq, a few study was focused on strategies at molecular scale in order to develop therapeutic strategy as a biological inhibitor of cancer cell uncontrolled proliferation, using transfection of synthetic RNA molecules into non-small cell lung carcinoma and blocking of CGIs of target mRNA promoter sequences. Many challenges remain ahead of their actual clinical application; however, when achieved, the use of miRNAs in the clinic is expected to enable great progress in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with NSCLC as therapeutic tools able to regress the growth of A549 lung epithelial cell line, in addition to lung fibroblast WI38 cell line as a control.

So, the aim of present study was undertaken to evaluate these agomirs, sense anatomic, and antisense sequences of were the most effective ncRNA as a therapeutic tools via gene silencing, due to regression of A549 lung epithelial cell line cell line.

Cell Culture & Transfection: for transfection of miRNA and lncRNAs, the selected cell lines were used (table 1).

Table 1: Cancerous and normal cell lines.

A549	CCL-185™	Homo Sapiens	Lung, epithelial cell, were isolated from the lung tissue of a White, 58-year-old male with lung cancer.
WI-38	ATCC® CCL-75™	Homo Sapiens	Lung fibroblast, WI-38 cells were isolated from the lung tissue of a 3-month-old, female, embryo

Growth Medium for Culturing Cell Lines

Cell growth medium ingredients (table 2), When preparing cell culture media, warmed all ingredients using water bath until they reach 37°C. It is necessary to prevent any cellular stress and optimal growth of cells.

Table 2: Cell line growth medium components. Catalogue No.

1	Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) High Glucose	Sigma	USA	Cat. No: DMEM-HXA
2	Penicillin/ Streptomycin			Cat. No: PS-B 100 ml
3	L-Glutamine			Cat No: GLN-B
4.	Fetal Bovine Serum			(FBS-12B Capricorn)

Transfection (Mimics & antagomirs)

The miRNA and lncRNA, that utilized in this study were listed in the table 3.

Table 3: miRNA and lncRNA used in the study.

	Brand, Origin	Orientation	Brand, Origin	Orientation
Mir34a	ABM(Canada)	Agomir	ABM(Canada)	Antagomir
Mir135a	ABM(Canada)	Agomir	ABM(Canada)	Antagomir
HOTAIR	ABM(Canada)	Sense	THERMO(UK)	Name Adv-Antisense

Gene Expression of the activity of lncRNA transfection

For RNA isolation, RiboEx and Hybrid-R (Catalogue No. 301-001 and 305-101 respectively), were supplied by GeneAll (South Korea). After lncRNA isolation,

cDNA synthesis phase was started. Hyper Script™ First strand synthesis kit(Catalog No,601-005) was supplied from GeneAll (S.Korea).

After preparing the cDNA mastermix, it was heated at 65°C for 5 min. incubated. After incubation, the mixture was taken on ice. Components whose names and quantities are indicated in the table below were added to the cDNA master mix and mixed homogeneously. After the cDNA was obtained, the Real-Time qPCR stage was started. RealAmp™SYBR qPCR Master mix was supplied by GeneAll,S.Korea (Primary information used for expression analysis is given in the table 5

Table 5: Primers used for Real Time qPCR.

Primer	Sequence	Brand,Origin
ACTB-F	CATGTACGTTGCTATCCAGGC	Oligomer,Turkey
ACTB-R	CTCCTTAATGTCACGCACGAT	Oligomer,Turkey
HOTAIR-F	AGTTCCACAGACCAACACCC	Oligomer,Turkey
HOTAIR-R	GTTCCATTCCACTGCGAAGC	Oligomer,Turkey

Gene expression of activity of miRNA transfection

The miRNA Isolation Kits (Ribo Ex, catalogue, No.301-001 and Hybrid-R miR NA,catalogue No 325-150) was supplied by GeneAll (S.Korea). After miRNA isolation, miRNA-cDNA synthesis phase was started. A specific"stem-loop primer"was designed for each miRNA to be investigated, and these primers were used in cDNA synthesis. While stem-loop primers (table 6) synthesized cDNA from miRNA, it is considered to be a very reliable method because it binds specifically with the miRNA sequence. Amplification mixture of miRNA-cDNA synthesis step was done by using the mastemix was supplied by Wizbio (S.Korea)and additional materials according to manufacturing company instructions.

Real-Time qPCR

(Stem-loop primers of miRNA expression)

After the miRNA-cDNA was obtained (table 8), the Real-Time qPCR stage was started. miRqGreen-ROX Master Mix kit was supplied by A.B.T.™ 2X (Catalogue No. Q04-02-01).

Table 6:Stem-Loop primers sequence used for miRNA-cDNA synthesis.

miRNA	Stem-Loop Primer Sequence	Brand, Origin
hsa-miR-34a (Stem-loop primer) (MIMAT0000255)	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCACTGGATACGACACAACC	Ella Biotech, Germany
hsa-miR-135a-5p (MIMAT0000428)	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGTCCGAGGTATTCGCACTGGATACGACTCACAT	
snRNA-RNU6 (ENST00000383898)	CGCTTCACGAATTTGCGTGTGTCAB.	

Table 8: miRNA primers used in Real Time qPCR.

miRNA Name	Forward direction	Reverse direction	Brand, origin
Hsa-miR-34a-5p	AACAGTGTGGCAGTGTCTTAG	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGT	Ella Biotech, Germany
Hsa-miR-135a-5p	CGCGGCCTATGGCTTTTTAT	GTCGTATCCAGTGCAGGGT	
snRNA-RNU6-F	GCTTCGGCAGCACATATACTAAAAT	CGCTTCACGAATTTGCGTGTGTCAT	

The amplification mixture used for Real-Time qPCR, composed of astermix supplied by Wizbio (S.Korea) and additional materials according to manufacturing company instructions.

Statistical analysis

Data were collected, summarized, analyzed and presented using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 25 and Microsoft Office Excel 2010. Chi-square test was used to study association between any two categorical variables. Odds ratio and 95% confidence interval was estimated to measure risk. The level of significance was considered at P-value of less 0.05 and highly significant level at 0.01 or less^{31,32}.

Results and Discussion

Transfected by using agomirs and sense

The present results of transfect amine fusion penetration for agomirs and antigomir miRNAs, ADV-sense-lncRNA, antisense-lncRNA, exposed diverse values of fold change were recognized with WI38 and A549 cell lines after transfection period .Diffusion of agomirs miRNA showed an elevation levels in A549cell line (mi-r34a, mir135a, HOTAIR) with comparison with WI38 cell line that presented low values in variation related with WI38cell line transfection with comparison with A549 cell line (table10).

Table (10): Transfection efficiency of agomirs miRNA and sense lncRNA related with WI38 and A549.

ncRNA (agomirs/sense)		WI 38	A549
		Induced fold	Induced fold
	Control	1	1
miRNA	mir34a	30.226893530	51.13463407
	Mir135a	28.984209803	45.442928556
lncRNA	HOTAIR	34.42321454	41.20417103

These results showed an increase of induction of transfection efficiency than control, that lead to these agomirs and sense will induce cell proliferation and cancerous cell growth, these results was similar to the other study³³⁻³⁶. HOTAIR, a long non-coding RNA, has been identified to stimulate H3K27 trimethylation, resulting in the downregulation of numerous genes. HOTAIR plays a role in promoting numerous kinds of tumors, including gastrointestinal stromal cancers, breast tumor, hepatocellular carcinoma and nasopharyngeal carcinoma. Additionally, HOTAIR has been found to promote tumorigenicity in lung carcinoma, consistent with its effects observed in other cell types.

Transfected by using antagomir and antisense

Transfection results of antagomir of miRNA, and antisense-lncRNA sequences exposed high values were found with A549 cell line, those (mir34a, mir135a, HOTAIR) presented an elevated in A549 in comparison with WI38 cell lines whereas showed low values in variation related with A549 comparison with WI38 cell lines (Table 11).

Table 11: Transfection efficiency of antagomir miRNA and antisense lncRNA related with A549 and WI38 cell lines.

ncRNA (antigomirs antisense)		WI 38	HT29
		Induced fold	Induced fold
	Control	1	1
miRNA	mir34a	0.864331028	7.720350832
	Mir135a	0.524751050	3.760990931
lncRNA	HOTAIR	0.434520972	4.861246094

These results showed a decrease from the agomirs and sense, that lead to these antagomirs and antisense reduce cell proliferation and cancerous cell growth, these results was same to the other study indicated that Antagomir-34a miRNA-34a is an important tumor suppressor miRNA that is commonly downregulated in cancer. When using an antagomir specifically designed to inhibit miRNA-34a^{37,38,40}.

Cell lines (A549 and WI38) viability after agomirs and sense transfected with XTT

The results of XTT staining revealed different values in growth of transfected cell lines with antigomirs and antisense sequences (mir34a, mir135 and antisense ADV-HOTAIR) shown an elevated in growth percent of WI38 cell line which make as growth factor this stimulated WI38 cell line production a while, the growth percent of A549 cell line production was reduced after transfected with these miRNAs and Lnc (Table 12).

Table 12: Transfection of agomir miRNA and sense ADV-lncRNA, then Cell lines viability (A549 and WI38) cell lines.

nc RNA	WI38	Cell Viability Mean (%)	Cell Viability SD (%)	A549	Cell Viability Mean (%)	Cell Viability SD (%)
	Control	100	8.101318824	Control	100	5.215543487
Agomirs /sense	mir34a	113.7909056	4.289286949	mir34a	95.7520613	4.166583312
	mir135	111.3693191	3.14365433	mir135	92.18063266	3.903285658
	HOTAIR	130.9982712	4.803955132	HOTAIR	97.32348981	2.963223140

Generally, previous results indicated that all agomirs, sense and antagomir and antisense sequences due to increase of WI38 cell line proliferation and due to decrease of A549 cell line proliferation. Many studies a round the world were concentrated on ncRNA transfection as a promising therapeutic technique with acceptable side effects with comprehensive with traditional therapy like chemo-radiotherapy⁴⁰, found MicroRNA (miR135a) miRNAs have emerged as important regulators in lung carcinogenesis, with certain members of the miR-135 family being identified as tumor suppressors in lung tumors.

In a study by Tian et al.^{41,42}, the downregulation of miR-135a in (NSCLC) cells was observed when compared to

usual epithelial cells in bronchial. The study demonstrated that miR-135a expression reserved the propagation, offensive, and metastasis in vitro of NSCLC cells.

Cell lines viability after antigomirs and antisense transfection

The results of XTT staining revealed different values in growth of transfected cell lines with antigomirs and antisense sequences (mir34a, mir135 and antisense ADV-HOTAIR) shown an elevated in growth percent of WI38 cell line which make as growth factor this stimulated WI38 cell line production a while, the growth percent of A549 cell line production was reduced after transfected with these miRNAs and Lnc RNA (table 13).

Table 13: Transfection of antigomir miRNA and antisense lncRNA, the Cell lines viability(A549 and WI38) cell lines.

	WI38	Cell Viability Mean(%)	Cell Viability SD(%)	HT29	Cell Viability Mean(%)	Cell Viability SD(%)
Antigomir □ antisense	Control	100	4.167206142	Control	100	6.027280761
	Mir34a	112.0286713	16.72361023	Mir34a	95.65134878	8.693863591
	Mir135	101.3058772	7.479697641	Mir135	90.08701986	4.588919037
	HOTAIR	130.3413432	9.87923659	HOTAIR	98.3027758	9.672687386

Many studies around the world were concentrated on ncRNA transfection as a promising therapeutic technique with acceptable side effects with comprehensive with traditional therapy like chemo-radiotherapy⁴³, found MicroRNA (miR135a) miRNAs have emerged as important regulators in lung carcinogenesis, with certain members of the miR-135 family being identified as tumor suppressors in lung tumors. These miRNAs exhibit downregulation in lung tumors and have been found to regulate various pathways of oncogenic, comprising the RAS pathway. Ongoing research continues to uncover additional latent oncogenic or cancer repressor miRNAs in lung cancer. In a study by⁴⁴, the downregulation of miR-135a in (NSCLC) cells was observed when compared to usual epithelial cells in bronchial. The study demonstrated that miR-135a expression reserved the propagation, offensive, and metastasis in vitro of NSCLC cells.

Ethics Consideration

This study is in accordance with the ethics committee of Al-Diwaniya teaching hospital, Iraq. A verbal agreement was obtained from participants in the study of the relative's pre-taking samples.

Conflict of interest: No known conflict of interest correlated with this publication.

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